

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COVID-19 VACCINOPROPHYLAXIS ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF TASHKENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10783082>

Abstract. *At the beginning of the year in which the study was carried out, the rate and duration of the incidence of the disease changed again. In particular, in January of this year, the record of high incidence among the population was recorded for two weeks and was assessed by the city sanitary and epidemiological service as a "high-intensity epidemic". However, it would be close to making sense to admit that the humoral immunity formed after morbidity and active vaccination among the population is weakened.*

Keywords: *COVID-19, coronavirus infection, epidemiology, prevention, vaccine prevention.*

Relevance. According to the results of the analysis of the epidemiological situation on COVID-19 in Tashkent, the manifestation of the epidemic process of the new coronavirus infection by space and time has primarily depended on the Shaksi approach of the population or the Shaksi attitude of people to this problem (wearing protective masks, maintaining social distance, disinfecting hands, being far from places where people gather a lot, etc.). The priority of the importance of the mechanism of especially air-drop transmission in the course of the epidemic process, the main direction in preventing the further development of the epidemic process of COVID-19, should be aimed at the activation of precisely privative prophylaxis among the population. In addition, we believe that the extremely strict organizational and preventive measures introduced in 2020 in the fight against coronavirus infection became the basis for the stabilization of the epidemic situation in our capital, like all regions of the Republic.

Research objective. Thus, unpleasant symptoms of the epidemiological situation in the city of Tashkent on COVID-19: year-round survival of the epidemic process, increased incidence rates among adults (especially the elderly), high epidemic outbreaks in collective conditions of people, chronic diseases of infection (diabetes mellitus, obesity, high arterial blood pressure, malignant tumors, those suffering from chronic forms of the upper respiratory organs, etc.) in individuals with severe clinical form and high mortality rates, the increasing occurrence of mild and unmarked forms of the disease among the population indicates that it is advisable to carry out mass vaccination among large-scale groups of the population.

Results. Since April 2021, mass vaccination against coronavirus has begun among residents of the city of Tashkent. During the analyzed period, 441,397 citizens (35.0%) were vaccinated with the AstraZeneca vaccine, of which 322,684 received the first dose and 118,713 received the second dose. With the Uzbek-Chinese vaccine ZF-UZ-VAK2001, 878,656 citizens (62.0%) were vaccinated, 736,814 were vaccinated with the first dose, 71,390 with the second dose, and 70,452 with the third dose. With the Russian-made "Sputnik V" vaccine, 35,614

residents of the city were vaccinated, which was 3.0% of those vaccinated from April 1 to May 12 of this year.

It should be said that groups vaccinated against COVID-19 in the city of Tashkent have been identified based on the threat of infection. Since April 2021, a phased vaccination of threatened groups has been carried out in the capital:

- performing vaccinoprophylaxis in a clear God and time-cut;
- epidemiological description of the vaccine drug;
- identifying tasks and methods used;
- calculation of economic indicators.

To date, more than 42% of the city's population has been vaccinated against COVID-19. Vaccinoprophylaxis or mass vaccination carried out on the basis of epidemiological guidelines has led to a decrease in the epidemic spread of the SARS-CoV2 virus in Tashkent. As a result of the expanding scale of mass vaccination in the population, the epidemiological risks associated with this infection began to decrease. The decrease in natural vastization caused by collective immunity and circulation of the SARS-CoV2 coronavirus, which was mainly formed due to vaccination, probably increased the susceptibility of adolescents and young children to the disease. As a result, COVID-19 began to harm not only adults, but also children. It is worth noting that mass vaccination did not significantly affect the main characteristics of the covid-19 epidemic process.

During the vaccination process, the principle of high-dose tolerance worldwide was not followed, that is, those affected during the incubation period were vaccinated.

Against the background of the conduct of vaccinoprophylaxis, an increase in the number of residents involved in the epidemic process, especially children, was noted. Thus, from mid-2021, the incidence of COVID-19 among residents of the city of Tashkent began to decline at a sharp pace, but by the end of the year, in January 2022, there was a further increase in the incidence rates. We admit that the condition that occurred was accompanied by the fact that all the vaccines created in the world had the effect, but with a low level of immunogenicity. In our opinion, this resistance of vaccines is directly related to the adjuvant in them. The aluminium hydroxide used by Chinese scientists as a placebo has resulted in the same postvaccinal complications in the primary and control groups.

Conclusion. In the years of studies, 2020-2021. The epidemic of the new coronavirus infection observed in Tashkent was marked by the strains SARA-CoV-2 and Delta, in the morning of 2021 and early 2022, the outbreak of the coronavirus strain "Omicron" was noted, this new strain was accompanied by much lighter clinical signs, and no deaths were observed. This is assessed by a decrease in virulence as a result of the increased prevalence of the virus in population populations.

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